

[ANDA approval process](#)

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Also available at: <https://pharmacyinfo.com/abbreviated-new-drug-application-anda/>

Abbreviated New Drug Application (ANDA)

1. What is an ANDA?

An ANDA is an Abbreviated New Drug Application submitted to the FDA for approval of a generic drug.

2. What is a generic drug?

A generic drug is a medication containing the same active ingredient(s) as a brand-name drug, but typically offered at a lower cost. It has the same dosage form, strength, route of administration, quality, performance characteristics, and intended use as the brand-name drug (called the Reference Listed Drug or RLD).

3. Why are ANDAs important?

ANDAs increase access to affordable medications for patients by promoting competition in the pharmaceutical market.

4. What information does an ANDA typically include?

An ANDA includes data on the generic drug's chemistry, manufacturing, controls, bioequivalence studies, and labeling. Unlike NDAs for new drugs, ANDAs don't require extensive pre-clinical or clinical trial data to establish safety and effectiveness, as this information is already established for the RLD.

5. Who can submit an ANDA?

Any company interested in obtaining approval for a generic drug can file an ANDA with the FDA.

6. How long does the ANDA approval process take?

The FDA review process for an ANDA typically takes between 12 and 16 months, assuming all submitted information is complete and accurate. This is significantly faster than the approval process for new drugs.

7. Are there different types of ANDAs?

Yes, there are two main categories:

- **505(j) ANDA:** This is for generic drugs that are identical to the RLD in dosage form, strength, route of administration, and active ingredient.
- **Petitioned ANDA:** This applies to generic drugs with some variations from the RLD, such as a different dosage form or inactive ingredients. Additional data or justification may be required for approval.

8. What are the fees associated with filing an ANDA?

The FDA charges annual fees for ANDA holders and a one-time fee for each ANDA application submitted. The specific fee amount depends on the size of the applicant company.

9. Where can I find more information about ANDAs?

The FDA website is a valuable resource for ANDA information, including forms, guidance documents, and regulations: <https://www.fda.gov/about-fda/fda-acronyms-abbreviations>